

Stobbe Reactions with Diethyl Homophthalate. Part II. 1'-Oxo-(2', 3'-4, 3)indenocoumarins and Related Compounds

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A synthesis of 3-phenylcoumarin-2'-carboxylic acid and its derivatives by a new adaptation of the Perkin synthesis and by the Stobbe condensation with diethyl homophthalate has been described. The work invalidates an earlier description of the compound by Buu-Hoï^{1a}. 1'-Oxo-(2', 3'-4, 3)indenocoumarins are shown to be formed during pyrolysis of the above acids in presence of copper bronze. During this work, new syntheses of the lactone of 2'-hydroxydibenzyl-2-carboxylic acid and indeno-(2', 3'-4, 3')coumarins have been effected.

In a certain investigation we required 3-phenylcoumarin-2'-carboxylic acid (I) and its derivatives. The compound has been described as having melting point 188° (incorrectly reported in *Chemical Abstract*¹ as 177°), obtained by the condensation of salicylaldehyde with diethyl homophthalate^{1a}. No analysis of the compound was reported and the described properties of the compound were incompatible with the structure. Thus the compound was described as soluble in hot water and was obtained unchanged on attempted reduction with sodium amalgam. Repetition of Buu-Hoï's experiment showed that salicylaldehyde did not react with diethyl homophthalate under the conditions described and his compound (m.p. 188°) was identified as homophthalic acid, arising obviously by the hydrolysis of the unchanged ester. The acid (I), however, has now been obtained directly by a new adaptation of the Perkin synthesis—the condensation of salicylaldehyde with homophthalic anhydride. This synthesis, as described in sequel, is general and has been used with advantage in other cases where obvious methods failed to provide the desired product.

1. *Chem. Abst.*, 1946, 40, 4046.
 1a. Buu-Hoï, *Compt. rend.*, 1944, 218, 942.

Another synthesis of the acid (I) was achieved by demethylation of *cis-o*-methoxybenzylidenehomophthalic acid with pyridine hydrochloride. The dihydrocoumarin (II) was obtained by the sodium amalgam reduction of the acid (I), but the catalytic reduction with palladised charcoal was not fruitful. Reduction with Adams' catalyst afforded an octahydro derivative, which appeared to be stereochemically homogeneous. Structure of the acid (I) was settled by decarboxylation with copper bronze-quinoline to 3-phenylcoumarin. The latter was also obtained on decarboxylating the reduced acid (II) with copper-quinoline.

A different result was obtained when the decarboxylation of the acids (I) and (II) was carried out with copper bronze at 280° to 300°. In both the cases, a beautiful red product sublimed in about 3-8% yield and the rest was a resinous product from which 3-phenylcoumarin could not be obtained. Better yield (about 8%) was obtained when palladised charcoal was used in place of copper bronze. Similarly, coloured products were obtained from coumarins (III), (IV), (V), and (VI), using palladised charcoal. On heating coumarin (IV) with copper bronze, the expected decarboxylated product (IVa) was only obtained.

The molecular weight of the coloured product isolated from (I) by Rast's (camphor) method was 235 and the analysis corresponded to $C_{16}H_8O_3$ (original compound *minus* one mole of water); it was ketonic in character (formation of mono-oxime and a mono-hydrazone). The compound was quinonoid in nature, reducible to a colorless leuco compound which was rapidly oxidised to the original coloured product. This indicated that the system $-CO-C=C-C=O$ was present. On oxidation with potassium permanganate, phthalic acid was isolated, indicating presence of a 1,2-substituted benzene ring. The compound showed carbonyl absorption at 5.77μ , 5.83μ ; 3-phenylcoumarin absorbs at 5.86μ and 3-phenyl-3,4-dihydrocoumarin absorbs at 5.68μ . On these grounds the compound is assigned the unusual structure (VII), the formation of which under pyrolytic conditions may be justified. The NMR spectrum of the compound was kindly examined by Dr. A. Melera of Varian Ag, Zürich. The substance is sparingly soluble in $CDCl_3$ and a rather weak spectrum is obtained; it shows presence of aromatic protons only, two of which, H^1 and H^2 , are shifted towards lower field value, as expected from the proposed formula.

(VII): $R=R'=H$.

(VIII): $R=OMe$; $R'=H$.

(IX): $R=H$; $R'=Me$.

Coloured lactones of the type (VIII) have been described by Borsche and Wannagat², who obtained them by cyclisation of 3-phenylcoumarin-4-carboxylic acid, prepared by the condensation of polyhydric phenols with phenyleyanopyruvic ester. In order

2. *Annalen*, 1950, 569, 81.

to prove conclusively the structures of our products, Borsche's compound (VIII) was synthesised by our method. Thus the Perkin synthesis of 2-hydroxy-4-methoxybenzaldehyde with homophthalic anhydride afforded directly acid (III). The alternative approach of securing the acid from 2,4-dimethoxybenzaldehyde and diethyl homophthalate was not fruitful. This acid on heating with copper bronze provided a violet-coloured product, identical with Borsche's compound (VIII). Similarly, Borsche's product (XI), derived from α -naphthol, was also synthesised by our procedure.

During this work we effected a new synthesis of the lactone (XII), prepared by Baker and co-workers³, because an impure specimen of this lactone also afforded a small quantity of the red product (VII) on heating with copper bronze. Baker prepared the lactone by cyclisation of the phenolic acid (XIV), which was obtained by the caustic fusion of *o*-methoxybenzylidenehomophthalic acid (XIII) under carefully controlled condition. In this reaction we find that the formation of compound (II) by demethylation is the first stage, because on interruption (and subsequent acidification) our dihydrocoumarin (II) is actually isolable. It was this impurity which accompanied Baker's lactone and was responsible for the formation of the red product, mentioned above. Indeed, a highly purified sample of the lactone, prepared by Baker's procedure or prepared by a different route (*vide infra*), was ineffectual in producing any oxo-indenocoumarin.

This lactone was prepared from *o*-methoxybenzylidenephthalide (XV) which was reduced to the dihydrophthalide (XVI) and then on caustic fusion to the stilbene carboxylic acid (XVIII). The compound is undoubtedly *trans*-oriented ($\lambda_{\max}^{\text{alc}}$ 290 m μ , 326 m μ ; log ϵ , 4.12 and 4.24). This was reduced, demethylated, and cyclised with trifluoroacetic anhydride to lactone (XII). On treatment with pyridine hydrochloride, compound (XVIII) yielded the *cis*-hydroxy acid (XVII) ($\lambda_{\max}^{\text{alc}}$ 280 m μ ; log ϵ , 3.63) which, however, could not be cyclised to the related unsaturated lactone (XXIII) although examination of models showed that the system should be capable of existence in spite of strain. The structure of this acid has been proved by its conversion to compound (XIV) by catalytic reduction.

Baker's lactone (XII) was reducible by lithium aluminium hydride to a phenolic alcohol, which on treatment with phosphorus tribromide-alkali afforded a poor yield of the heterocycle (XIX); most of the product was a polymer, as might be expected on stereochemical grounds.

A direct synthesis of the indeno-coumarin system (XX) has been achieved by the condensation of ethyl 2-hydrindone-1-carboxylate⁴ with polyhydric phenols, such as, resorcinol or phloroglucinol, with hydrogen chloride in absolute ethanol (cf. Robinson *et al.*⁵). The product (XXI) derived from resorcinol was methylated to (XXII). This strongly fluorescent compound differed from Borsche's product (VIII) in having a $\text{-CH}_2\text{-}$ group in place of >C=O . We attempted to decompose the monohydrazone of (VIII) with potassium hydroxide in diethylene glycol and although we obtained a strongly fluorescent material, we failed to isolate the product (XXII) in substance. The reverse option, namely, oxidation of $\text{>CH}_2 \rightarrow \text{>C=O}$ by selenium dioxide in different solvents, did not hold much promise.

3. Baker *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 1447.

4. Perkin (jr.) and Titley, *ibid.*, 1922, 121, 1566.

5. Crabtree and Robinson, *ibid.*, 1918, 113, 859.

(XII)

(XIII)

(XIV)

(XV)

(XVI)

(XVII): R=OH.
(XVIII): R=OMe.

(XIX)

(XX): R=H.
(XXI): R=OH.
(XXII): R=OMe.

(XXIII)

*EXPERIMENTAL

3-(2'-Carboxyphenyl)coumarin (I).—(a). A mixture of *o*-methoxybenzaldehyde (2.7 g.) and diethyl homophthalate (4.7 g.) was added to a solution of sodium (0.5 g.) in dry ethanol (25 ml) and the mixture was refluxed on a water bath for 4 hours. The mixture was cooled,

*All melting points are uncorrected.

diluted with water, and the unchanged material extracted with ether. The aqueous solution was boiled with NaOH (10%, 15 ml) for 1/2 hour and then acidified to furnish *o*-methoxybenzylidenehomophthalic acid (4.5 g.) which crystallised from acetic acid in cream-coloured prisms, m.p. 190-91°. Baker *et al.*³, who prepared the compound by the Perkin synthesis, reported m.p. 195°.

The foregoing acid (0.5 g.) was mixed with pyridine hydrochloride (2 g.) and heated at 200-210° in a current of dry carbon dioxide. The melt was cooled, treated with HCl (dil.), and warmed on a water bath for 20 minutes. The product (I) separating was crystallised from ethanol in colorless needles, m.p. 267°, yield, 0.2 g. (Found: C, 72.2; H, 3.8. C₁₆H₁₆O₄ requires C, 72.2; H, 3.8%). $\lambda_{\max}^{\text{alc}}$ 289 m μ , 294 m μ , 316 m μ (log ϵ , 4.10, 4.11, 4.06).

On employing hydrobromic acid (48%) in acetic acid (3 hours), a poor yield (30%) of the compound was obtained.

The *methyl ester*, prepared by diazomethane, crystallised from ethanol in colorless needles, m.p. 153-54°. (Found: C, 72.8; H, 4.4. C₁₇H₁₈O₄ requires C, 72.9; H, 4.3%).

(b). A mixture of salicylaldehyde (1.2 g.), homophthalic anhydride (1.6 g.), fused potassium acetate (1.99 g.), and acetic anhydride (3.5 g.) was heated in an oil bath at 160-65° for 16 hours. After decomposing the mixture with water, the solid separating was extracted with sodium carbonate. The alkaline extract on acidification furnished the acid (I) (1.4 g.); m.p. and mixed m.p. 267° (from ethanol).

3-(2'-Carboxyphenyl)-3,4-dihydrocoumarin (II) was obtained by reduction of the foregoing coumarin with sodium amalgam, m.p. 200-201° (from dilute acetic acid), or by demethylation of *o*-methoxybenzylhomophthalic acid (XIII) (Baker *et al.*³) (3.0 g.) with hydrobromic acid (10 ml, 48%) in acetic acid (10 ml) for 3 hours; yield 1.8 g. (Found: C, 71.3; H, 4.7. C₁₆H₁₄O₄ requires C, 71.6; H, 4.5%).

The *methyl ester*, prepared by diazomethane, crystallised from methanol in colorless prisms, m.p. 122-24°. (Found: C, 72.1; H, 5.0. C₁₇H₁₄O₄ requires C, 72.3; H, 5.0%).

Whereas coumarin (I) was recovered unchanged on attempted hydrogenation with palladised charcoal in acetic acid, catalytic reduction of the acid (0.2 g.) with Adams' catalyst (0.1 g.) in acetic acid (5 ml) did not stop with the absorption of one mole of hydrogen. Approximately 4 moles of hydrogen were absorbed, affording an *octahydro derivative*, which crystallised from acetic acid in prisms, m.p. 169-70°. (Found: C, 70.5; H, 6.0. C₁₆H₁₆O₄ requires C, 70.6; H, 5.9%).

Decarboxylation.—Decarboxylation of the acid (0.7 g.) was done by boiling in quinoline (10 ml) with copper bronze (0.3 g.) for 5 hours. Isolated in the usual manner, the product (0.26 g.) was identified as 3-phenylcoumarin; m.p. and mixed m.p. 142°. Decarboxylation of (II) in the same way also provided 3-phenylcoumarin, m.p. 142° (by dehydrogenation), undepressed on admixture with an authentic sample prepared by the method of Oglialoro⁶ ($\lambda_{\max}^{\text{alc}}$ 324 m μ ; log ϵ , 4.17).

o-Methoxybenzylidene-4-methylhomophthalic Acid.—(a). A mixture of *o*-methoxy-

6. *Ber.*, 1879, 12, 2367.

benzaldehyde (2.04 g.) and diethyl 4-methylhomophthalate⁷(3.75 g.) was added to a solution of sodium methoxide (0.34 g. of Na in 22 ml methanol) and the solution was refluxed for 6 hours. After removing methanol by distillation, the solid residue was dissolved in water, hydrolysed by boiling with a 10% NaOH solution, and then acidified to afford the *benzylidene derivative* (2.6 g.), which crystallised from acetic acid in pale yellow needles, m.p. 225° (evolution of gas). (Found: C, 68.5; H, 5.1. $C_{18}H_{16}O_3$ requires C, 69.2; H, 5.1%).

The *methyl ester*, prepared with diazomethane, crystallised from methanol in colorless prisms, m.p. 130°. (Found: C, 70.5; H, 5.5. $C_{20}H_{18}O_3$ requires C, 70.6; H, 5.9%).

On reduction of the above acid with sodium amalgam, *o-methoxybenzyl-4-methylhomophthalic acid* was obtained which crystallised from ethanol in colorless needles, m.p. 110°. (Found: C, 68.7; H, 5.9. $C_{18}H_{18}O_3$ requires C, 68.7; H, 5.9%).

3-(2'-Carboxy-4'-methylphenyl)coumarin (IV).—(a). The foregoing acid (0.5 g.) was demethylated by heating with pyridine hydrochloride (5 g.) at 200-210° for 1½ hours in an atmosphere of carbon dioxide. The compound crystallised from ethanol in colorless needles, m.p. 257°, yield 0.25 g.

(b). A mixture of salicylaldehyde (0.8 g.), 4-methylhomophthalic acid (1 g.), acetic anhydride (2.3 ml), and fused potassium acetate (1.2 g.) was heated in an oil bath at 170-80° for 16 hours. The mixture was worked up in the usual manner and the coumarin purified by dissolving in sodium carbonate solution, followed by acidification. The compound (0.25 g.) crystallised from ethanol in colorless needles; m.p. and mixed m.p. 257°. (Found: C, 73.5; H, 4.6. $C_{17}H_{12}O_4$ requires C, 72.7; H, 4.2%).

7-Methoxy-3-(2'-carboxyphenyl)coumarin (III).—(a). A mixture of 2,4-dimethoxybenzaldehyde (4.0 g.) and diethyl homophthalate (5.6 g.) was added to a solution of sodium (0.4 g.) in dry methanol (34 ml) and the mixture was refluxed on a water bath for 8 hours. The mixture was cooled, diluted with water, and the unchanged material extracted with ether. The aqueous solution was boiled with 10% NaOH (30 ml) for half an hour and then acidified to provide 2,4-dimethoxybenzylidenehomophthalic acid (4.35 g.) which crystallised from acetic acid in pale yellow needles, m.p. 221°, turning yellow at 187°. (Found: C, 65.3; H, 5.1. $C_{18}H_{16}O_6$ requires C, 65.9; H, 4.8%).

The *methyl ester*, prepared by diazomethane, crystallised from ethanol in colorless needles, m.p. 116°. (Found: C, 67.1; H, 6.0. $C_{20}H_{20}O_6$ requires C, 67.3; H, 5.6%).

On reduction of the above acid with sodium amalgam, 2,4-dimethoxybenzylhomophthalic acid was obtained in quantitative yield. It was crystallised from acetic acid in colorless needles, m.p. 171-72°. (Found: C, 64.2; H, 5.0. $C_{18}H_{18}O_6$ requires C, 64.4; H, 5.4%).

Demethylation.—Demethylation of the 2, 4-dimethoxybenzylidenehomophthalic acid or its reduction product with pyridine hydrochloride or with hydrobromic acid did not afford any crystalline product.

(b). A mixture of 2-hydroxy-4-methoxybenzaldehyde (1.52 g.), homophthalic anhydride (1.62 g.), acetic anhydride (3.5 ml), and fused potassium acetate (1.96 g.) was heated in an oil bath at 170-80° for 16 hours. The mixture was extracted with boiling sodium carbonate

solution. On acidification, coumarin (III) was obtained, crystallising from acetic acid in colorless needles, m.p. 220-21°, yield 1.0 g. (Found: C, 68.7; H, 4.6. $C_{17}H_{12}O_2$ requires C, 68.9; H, 4.5%).

5,6-Benzo-3-(*o*-carboxyphenyl)coumarin (V) was similarly prepared from 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde (1.7 g.), homophthalic anhydride (1.6 g.), acetic anhydride (4 ml), and fused potassium acetate (2 g.) at 180-90° for 12 hours. The coumarin (0.9 g.) crystallised from ethanol in cream-coloured needles, m.p. 267°. (Found: C, 76.1; H, 4.2. $C_{20}H_{12}O_4$ requires C, 75.9; H, 3.7%).

7,8-Benzo-3-(*o*-carboxyphenyl) coumarin (VI) was similarly prepared from 1-hydroxy-2-naphthaldehyde⁸ as colorless prismatic needles, m.p. 278° (from ethanol). (Found: C, 76.2; H, 4.1. $C_{20}H_{12}O_4$ requires C, 75.9; H, 3.7%).

3-(*o*-Methoxybenzyl)phthalide (XVI).—A mixture of *o*-methoxyphenylacetic acid (3.4 g.), phthalic anhydride (3.0 g.) and fused sodium acetate (0.1 g.) was heated at 240° in a metal bath for 3 hours. After cooling, sufficient ethanol (30 ml) was added and the yellow solid was filtered. *o*-Methoxybenzylidene-phthalide (XV) was obtained as wooly needles, m.p. 157-59°, yield 2.1 g. (Found: C, 75.9; H, 4.9. $C_{16}H_{12}O_3$ requires C, 76.2; H, 4.8%).

Reduction of the phthalide (0.5 g.) in boiling KOH (1.25 g. in 3 ml water) with zinc dust (0.75 g.) was carried out during 30 minutes. The mixture was diluted, filtered, and acidified to provide *o*-methoxybenzylphthalide which crystallised from ethanol in colorless wooly needles, m.p. 76-77°, yield 0.37 g. (Found: C, 75.5; H, 5.4. $C_{16}H_{14}O_3$ requires C, 75.6; H, 5.5%).

trans-2'-Methoxystilbene-2-carboxylic Acid (XVIII).—A solution of the foregoing phthalide (1.0 g.) in KOH (0.5 g. in 1 ml water) was heated at 140°, the temperature being slowly raised to 200° at reduced pressure (300 mm) for 1½ hours. The mixture was cooled, diluted, and acidified to afford the acid (0.38 g.), crystallising from acetic acid in colorless needles, m. p. 163-65°. λ_{max}^{alc} 290 m μ , 326 m μ (log ϵ , 4.15, 4.24). (Found: C, 75.3; H, 5.7. $C_{16}H_{14}O_3$ requires C, 75.6; H, 5.5%).

The acid (0.5 g.) on demethylation with pyridine hydrochloride (2 g.) at 200-10° for 2 hours provided a gummy mass, which was taken up in ether and the acid extracted by sodium carbonate. cis-2-Hydroxystilbene-2'-carboxylic acid (XVII) crystallised from acetic acid in prisms, m.p. 175°. λ_{max}^{alc} 280 m μ (log ϵ , 3.63). (Found: C, 74.7; H, 5.1. $C_{15}H_{12}O_3$ requires C, 75.0; H, 5.0%).

The acid was recovered unchanged on treatment with trifluoroacetic anhydride. The acid on catalytic reduction afforded 2'-hydroxydibenzyl-2-carboxylic acid (XIV), m.p. 141°. Attempted demethylation with hydrobromic acid afforded halogenated products.

Catalytic reduction of the acid (XVIII) in acetic acid with palladised charcoal (5%) was quantitative and 2'-methoxydibenzyl-2-carboxylic acid (Baker *et al.*⁹) was isolated as colorless shining leaflets; m.p. and mixed m.p. 115°.

8. Hamada, *J. Chem. Soc., Japan*, 1952, 73, 47.

Demethylation of this acid (0.5 g.) with hydrobromic acid (7 ml, 48%) in acetic acid (7 ml) for 3 hours furnished the phenolic acid (0.43 g.), crystallising from benzene in colorless, needles, m.p. 141°. Baker *et al.*³ reported m.p. 140-41°. Mixed m.p. with a specimen, prepared by Baker's procedure, was not depressed. The compound was cyclised by heating with trifluoroacetic anhydride (cf. Baker *et al.*³) to afford the lactone (XII), m.p. 114°. $\lambda_{\max}^{\text{alc}}$ 283 m μ , 294 m μ (log ϵ , 3.98, 3.95).

o-Methoxybenzylhomophthalic acid (XIII) (1.0 g.) was carefully heated to fusion with KOH (5.0 g.) and maintained in the fused state for about 2 minutes. The melt was cooled, dissolved in water, and filtered. The filtrate on acidification provided a crystalline material, which on several recrystallisations from benzene melted at 200-201°, undepressed on admixture with an authentic sample of 3-(2'-carboxylphenyl)-3,4-dihydrocoumarin (II). The latter acid (1.0 g.) on similar alkali fusion (5.0 g.) afforded 2'-hydroxydibenzyl-2-carboxylic acid (XIV) which on recrystallisation from benzene melted at 140-41°, undepressed when mixed with an authentic sample.

Action of Copper-bronze or Palladised Charcoal on 3-o-Carboxyphenylcoumarin or its Dihydro Derivative.—A mixture of the coumarin (1.25 g.) and copper bronze or palladised charcoal (0.25 g.) was heated gradually in a metal bath. Evolution of gas started at 245°, which became rapid at 255-60°. Some carbon dioxide gas was evolved. A crystalline red mass gradually sublimed, leaving a dark resinous mass. The sublimed material was dissolved in benzene and passed through deactivated alumina. On two or three crystallisations from benzene, 1'-*oxo*-(2',3'-4,3)indenocoumarin (VII) was obtained as attractive red needles (yield 3 to 8%), m.p. 290-92°. [Found: C, 77.0; H, 3.3, M.W. (Rast), 235. C₁₆H₉O₃ requires C, 77.4; H, 3.2%; M.W., 248]. 3-Phenylcoumarin could not be detected as a product of decarboxylation.

UV spectrum: $\lambda_{\max}^{\text{alc}}$ 263 m μ (log ϵ , 4.31), 280-81 m μ (log ϵ , 4.41).

IR spectrum: Carbonyl absorption at 5.77 μ , 5.83 μ .

The *oxime*, prepared in pyridine, crystallised from acetic acid in beautiful orange needles, m.p. 267-68° (decomp.). (Found: N, 5.0. C₁₆H₉O₃N requires N, 5.3%).

The *hydrazone* melted at 171-72°, but could not be obtained in an analytically pure condition.

Oxidation.—Oxidation of the compound (0.1g.) in boiling 3% alkaline KMnO₄ solution (30ml) was complete in 1½ hours. On isolation, the products were identified as phthalic acid (by mixed m.p. determination) and probably salicylic acid (ferric test).

Reduction.—(a). On reduction with zinc dust in acetic acid, a colorless solution of the leuco compound was obtained, which was precipitated by addition of water. The crystalline substance turned reddish at 120° and melted at 135-42°, turning deep red. On keeping, the substance was completely oxidised back to the original compound.

(b). *Clemmensen Reduction.*—The compound (0.2 g.) was boiled under reflux with a mixture of zinc amalgam (10 g.), toluene (20 ml), glacial acetic acid (5 ml), and HCl (40ml,

1:1) for 120 hours. The almost colorless toluene layer was separated and the aqueous layer was diluted and extracted with ether. The combined solvents were removed and the residue was chromatographed in benzene solution on alumina and eluted with benzene. The first fraction, which eluted a yellow material, m.p. 129-37°, could not be purified and exhibited a yellowish green fluorescence with sulphuric acid. The second fraction, which eluted a pink material, practically gave traces of a solid. The column was next eluted with ethanol. This eluate crystallised after a long time from ethanol, m.p. 182-94°, showing carbonyl absorption at 5.85 μ .

Catalytic Reduction.—The compound (0.1g.) was dissolved in acetic acid (25 ml) and hydrogenated at room temperature with Adams' catalyst (0.05g.). About 60 ml of hydrogen was absorbed and the colorless solution filtered and concentrated to afford a viscous mass, which solidified after a long time; m.p. 120-24° (shrinkage at 112-14°). The compound was alcoholic in nature (Zerewitinoff test). This compound could not be examined further on account of paucity of the material.

1'-Oxo-6'-methyl-(2'3'-4,3)indenocoumarin (IX).—3-(2'-Carboxy-4'-methylphenyl)-coumarin (0.5g.) was intimately mixed with palladised charcoal (0.2g., 15%) and heated in a metal bath. White fumes were evolved, followed by red vapours which condensed. The crystalline sublimate was dissolved in benzene and passed through a deactivated alumina column. The violet solution was concentrated to provide the *oxo-indenocoumarin (IX)* as violet needles, which on recrystallisation melted at 266-67°. (Found: C, 74.5; H, 3.9. C₁₇H₁₀O₃ requires C, 75.0; H, 3.9%).

On heating with copper bronze, 3-(2'-carboxy-4'-methylphenyl)coumarin furnished a decarboxylated product, 3-(4'-methylphenyl)coumarin (IVa) which was purified by filtering the benzene solution through an alumina column. On crystallisation from benzene, the coumarin was obtained as pale yellow needles, m.p. 160°. (Found: C, 81.7; H, 5.1. C₁₇H₁₂O₂ requires C, 82.2; H, 4.8%).

7-Methoxy-1'-oxo-(2'3'-4,3)indenocoumarin (VIII), similarly prepared from 3-(*o*-carboxyphenyl)-7-methoxycoumarin, crystallised from benzene in violet needles, m.p. 243°, underpressed on admixture with an authentic sample prepared by the method of Borsche and Wannagat². The IR spectrum showed carbonyl absorption at 5.77 μ and 5.85 μ . The compound developed a red colour with sulphuric acid.

The *hydrazone*, prepared in ethanol by heating with hydrazine hydrate, crystallised from ethanol in yellow needles, m.p. 242° (decomp.). (Found: N, 9.4. C₁₇H₁₂O₃N₂ requires N, 9.6%).

The *oxime*, prepared in pyridine, crystallised from acetic acid in beautiful orange needles, m.p. 264° (decomp.). (Found: N, 5.0. C₁₇H₁₁O₄N requires N, 4.8%). The IR spectrum showed absorptions at 3.01 μ and 5.83 μ .

Catalytic Reduction.—A suspension of the compound in acetic acid rapidly absorbed one mole of hydrogen in presence of palladised charcoal or platinic oxide to form a colorless solution, exhibiting bluish fluorescence. On leaving to the atmosphere, the solution was rapidly oxidised, depositing the original material.

On heating 7-methoxy-3-(*o*-carboxyphenyl)coumarin with copper bronze in quinoline, 3-phenyl-7-methoxycoumarin was obtained which crystallised from benzene in colorless needles; m.p. and mixed m.p. 123-24°. The authentic sample was prepared by the method of Oglialoro⁶.

5,6-Benzo-1'-oxo-(2',3'-4, 3)indenocoumarin(X) was similarly obtained from 5,6-benzo-3-(*o*-carboxyphenyl)coumarin(V). It was crystallised from benzene in brownish red crystals, m.p. 242°, yield, 0.78 g. (Found: C, 80.4; H, 3.3. $C_{20}H_{10}O_3$ requires C, 80.5; H, 3.3%).

7,8-Benzo-1'-oxo-(2',3'-4, 3)indenocoumarin (XI) was crystallised from benzene in brownish violet crystals, m.p. 258°. Unfortunately the material at hand was too meagre for further purification; mixed m.p. with an authentic sample (m.p. 262°), prepared by Borsche's method, was 258°.

7-Hydroxy-(2',3'-4, 3)indenocoumarin (XXI).—A solution of 1-ethoxycarbonylindan-2-one (3 g.) and resorcinol (3.2 g.) in dry ethanol (15 ml) was saturated with dry HCl gas at 0° and the mixture left overnight in an ice chest. Yellowish crystals (2.8 g.) of the coumarin(XXI) separated, which were recrystallised from nitrobenzene in light yellow needles, m.p. 300°. The compound is almost insoluble in benzene, acetone, and acetic acid and exhibits a violet fluorescence in sulphuric acid. (Found: C, 76.4; H, 4.0. $C_{16}H_{10}O_3$ requires C, 76.8; H, 4.0%).

On methylation in acetone, the *methyl ether*(XXII) was produced, which on recrystallisation from ethanol was obtained as colorless needles, m.p. 158°. (Found: C, 77.0; H, 4.5. $C_{17}H_{12}O_3$ requires C, 77.3; H, 4.5%).

5,7-Dihydroxy-(2',3'-4, 3)indenocoumarin was similarly prepared from phloroglucinol in excellent yield. The compound crystallised from nitrobenzene in a yellowish crystalline mass, m.p. 300°. (Found: C, 72.1; H, 3.8. $C_{16}H_{10}O_4$ requires C, 72.2; H, 3.8%).

The *dimethyl ether*, obtained on methylation, crystallised from ethanol in colorless needles, m.p. 180-81°. (Found: C, 73.2; H, 4.9. $C_{18}H_{14}O_4$ requires C, 73.5; H, 4.8%).

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